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Host plants, distribution, parasitoids and predators of *Tuta absoluta* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) as well as population dynamics of this pest infest different crops and distributed in different Governorates in Egypt

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The tomato leaf miner *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) is a dangerous pest of the host plants of the family Solanaceae, especially tomatoes, and it is difficult to control. The aim of the present work is to study host plants, distribution, parasitoids, predators, and population dynamics of this pest infesting different crops and regions in different governorates in Egypt. The results indicated that this pest infested five host plants. These are tomato, *solanum lycopersicom* (L.), potato, *solanum tuberosum* (L.), eggplant, *Solanum melongena* (L.), black nightshade, *Solanum nigrum* (L.) and pepper, *Capsicum annuum* (L.). it is distributed in 14 governorates in Egypt. These are Alexandria, Aswan, Behara, Beni-Suef, Dommiette, El-Dakahleia, El-Gharbia, El-Isamlia, El-Monifia, El-Qalubia, El-Sharkia. Giza, Kafr El-Sheikh and Marsa Matrouh. Also, this pest is associated with 11 parasitoids and 6 predators. The parasitoids were *Trichogramma achaeae* (Nagaraja and Nagarkatti), *Trichogramma evanesens* Westwood, *Trichogramma euproctidis* Girault, *Trichogrammatoidea bactrae* Nagaraja (Hymenoptera: Trichogrammatidae), *Bracon* sp. (Hymenoptera: Braconidae), *Pteromalus* sp. (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae), *Eulophus* sp., *Diglyphus* sp. and *Necremnus tutae* (Reuter) (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae) new record in Egypt (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae), *Elasmus* sp. (Hymenoptera: Elasmidae), *Telenomus* sp. (Hymenoptera: Scelionidae), *Bracon nigricans* Szépligeti (Hymenoptera: Braconidae) and the predators were *Macrolophus caliginosus* Wagner, *Nesidiocoris tenuis* (Reuter), *Macrolophus pygmaeus* (Rambur) (Hemiptera: Miridae), *Chrysoperla carnea* (Steph) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) and *Amblyseius swirskii* Athias-Henriot (Acari: Phytoseiidae). The present work also studied the population dynamics of the tomato leaf miners *T. absoluta* on tomato, *S. lycopersicom*, potato, *S. tuberosum*, eggplant, *S. melongena* (L.) and pepper, *C. annuum* in Giza and Qalyubiya Governorates. The general conclusion of the results of population dynamics of the pest and its natural enemies. It peaked in June 2025, and the most important parasitoids and predators are *T. achaeae* and *N. tenuis*, respectively.

Introduction

The tomato leaf miner *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) is a neotropical oligophagous insect, which attacks solanaceous crops. Since the 1960s it has become one of the key pests of tomato crop in many South American countries (Bahamondes and Mallea, 1969) and recorded in Egypt in the middle of 2009 (Mohammed, 2010). Larvae can damage tomato plants during all growth stages, producing large galleries in their leaves, burrowing stalks, and apical buds, green and ripe fruits. It can cause important yield losses in different production regions and under diverse production systems (Cely *et al.*, 2006). In early infestation, newly emerged neonates (First instar) penetrate the leaf into the mesophyll layer and feed between the lower and upper surfaces of the leaf to form small and transparent mines. As a result of continuous feeding by the larvae, the irregular mines combine together and eventually form galleries (Nakano and Paulo, 1983 and Branco *et al.*, 1987).

Many studies highlighted that *T. absoluta* has expanded its host range in the newly invaded countries and some weeds can act as an alternative host (Abbes *et al.*, 2016). Furthermore, weather factors in the newly invaded regions can modify TLM's generation time, the number of generations during a planting or growing season, annual generation peaks, and the biological properties among generations (Abolmaaty *et al.*, 2010). The relatively high numbers of m/t/w that were observed from the beginning of winter seasons might be considered as extend from summer seasons due to relatively high larval population by the end of earlier

summer and TLM male population increases with warm weather and moderate temperatures during May then decreased with higher temperatures (Awad *et al.*, 2018).

Natural enemies such as parasitoids and predators were used successfully in biological control of *T. absoluta*. Many authors have been working on the natural enemies of *T. absoluta* in the world and Egypt *e.g.* Molla *et al.* (2009), Guenaoui and Bensaad (2011), Mahdi *et al.* (2011), Molla *et al.* (2011), El-Arnaouty and Kortam (2012), Giorgini *et al.* (2012), Zappalà *et al.* (2012), Al-Gerrawy *et al.* (2013), Gabarra *et al.* (2013), Abbes *et al.* (2014), Payer *et al.* (2015), Abdelmaksoud *et al.* (2016), Perdikis *et al.* (2016) and El-Said *et al.* (2022).

The present work is to study the survey of *T. absoluta* and its natural enemies in different Governorates, as well as the population dynamics of this pest on different crops in different Governorates in Egypt.

Materials and methods

1. Survey of host plants, distribution, parasitoids and predators of *Tuta absoluta*:

Samples of tomato leaves infested with *T. absoluta* were collected from fields in different Governorates during 2025. Leaves were placed in rearing boxes covered with muslin cloth and secured with rubber bands. Emerging parasitoids were collected and kept in ethanol 70%. Parasitoids were identified in Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research center. However, predators associated with *T. absoluta* were easily recognized and identified.

2. Population dynamics of tomato leaf miners *T. absoluta* and its natural enemies infest different crops and distribute in different Governorates:

Population dynamics of the tomato leaf miners *T. absoluta* were studied on tomato, *solanum lycopersicom* (L.), potato, *solanum tuberosum* (L.), eggplant, *Solanum melongena* (L.) and, pepper, *Capsicum annuum* (L.) in Giza and Qalyubiya Governorates. The different crop were cultivated using standard agricultural practices, and no insecticides were applied during the summer plantation. In order to investigate the population dynamics, 30 leaves were selected. Weekly samples were collected over a three-month period. A total of 30 leaves were haphazardly sampled from the designated different crops and placed in polyethylene bags for subsequent counting under a stereomicroscope and were counted.

To identify the parasitoids of the pest, the bark of each plant sample was carefully removed from a 30 cm section of the vine trunk, along with 100 leaves and 25 bunches. These plant parts were then examined in the laboratory to count the nymphs and adult pests. Subsequently, the bark, leaves, and bunches were placed in glass jars weighing one pound each (with 10 jars utilized weekly). A filter paper disc was placed at the bottom of each jar to absorb any moisture, while the jars were covered with polyethylene sheets secured with rubber bands, featuring small holes for ventilation. Inside each jar, a small plastic container held a cotton wool soaked in a 10% sucrose solution to provide nourishment for the emerging parasitoids. After the parasitoids emerged, they were collected and placed in well-ventilated tubes containing 70% alcohol, then sent to Prof. Dr. S. Abd-Rabou at the Plant Protection Institute of the Ministry of Agriculture in Egypt for identification.

Results and discussion

1. Host plants of *Tuta absoluta* in Egypt:

Tomato, *solanum lycopersicom* (L.), Potato, *solanum tuberosum* (L.), Eggplant, *Solanum melongena* (L.) Black nightshade, *Solanum nigrum* (L.) and Pepper, *Capsicum annuum* (L.)

2. Distribution of *Tuta absoluta* in Egypt:

Alexandria, Aswan, Behara, Beni-Suef, Dommiette, El-Dakahleia, El-Gharbia, El-Isamlia, El-Monifia, El-Qalubia, El-Sharkia. Giza, Kafr El-Sheikh and Marsa Matrouh

3. Parasitoids of *Tuta absoluta* in Egypt:

Trichogramma achaeae (Nagaraja and Nagarkatti), *Trichogramma evanesens* Westwood, *Trichogramma euproctidis* Girault, *Trichogrammatoidea bactrae* Nagaraja (Hymenoptera: Trichogrammatidae), *Bracon* sp. (Hymenoptera: Braconidae), *Pteromalus* sp. (Hymenoptera: Pteromalidae), *Eulophus* sp., *Diglyphus* sp. and *Necremnus tuta* (Reuter) (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae) New record In Egypt (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae), *Elasmus* sp. (Hymenoptera: Elasmidae), *Telenomus* sp. (Hymenoptera: Scelionidae), *Bracon nigricans* Szépligeti (Hymenoptera: Braconidae).

4. Predators of *Tuta absoluta* in Egypt:

Macrolophus caliginosus Wagner, *Nesidiocoris tenuis* (Reuter), *Macrolophus pygmaeus* (Rambur) (Hemiptera: Miridae), *Chrysoperla carnea* (Steph) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae) and *Amblyseius swirskii* Athias-Henriot (Acari: Phytoseiidae).

5. Population dynamics of tomato leaf miners *Tuta absoluta* and its natural enemies infest different crops and distributed in different Governorates:

The results of *T. absoluta* population dynamics on tomato, *S. lycopersicom*, potato, *S. tuberosum*, eggplant, *S. melongena* (L.) and pepper, *C. annuum* in Giza and Qalyubiya Governorates over 2025 year are presented in Tables (1-8).

Tables (1-4) showed that the highest populations of *T. absoluta* eggs and larvae in Giza Governorate of tomato, *S. lycopersicom*, potato, *S. tuberosum*, eggplant, *S. melongena* (L.) and pepper, *C. annuum* infested by this pest were 653 and 901; 655 and 874; 436 and 688 and 532 and 587 individuals/ sample, respectively. The highest population of parasitoids and predators on tomato in Giza, the parasitoids *T. achaeae*, *T. evanesens*, *T. euproctidis*, *Pteromalus* sp., *Eulophus* sp., *Diglyphus* sp., the predators were *M. caliginosus*, *N. tenuis* and *A. swirskii* were 96, 27, 35, 3, 5, 3, 4, 51 and 4 individuals/sample, respectively. The highest population of parasitoids and predators on eggplant in Giza, the parasitoids *T. achaeae*, *Pteromalus* sp., *Diglyphus* sp., *B. nigricans*, the predators were *M. caliginosus*, *N. tenuis* and *C. carnea* were 55, 2, 3, 3, 3, 29 and 2 individuals/sample, respectively. The highest population of parasitoids and predators on potatoes in Giza, the parasitoids *T. achaeae*, *T. bactrae*, *Bracon* sp., *Pteromalus* sp., *Diglyphus* sp., the predators *N. tenuis* and *A. swirskii* were 14, 2, 3, 2, 36 and 6 individuals/sample, respectively. The highest population of parasitoids and predators on pepper in Giza, the parasitoids *T. achaeae*, *T. evanesens*,

T. bactrae, *Elasmus* sp., *Telenomus* sp., *B. nigricans*, *N. tutae* and the predators were *N. tenuis*, *M. pygmaeus* and *C. carnea* were 37, 6, 3, 1, 12, 5, 25, 3 and 5 individuals/sample, respectively.

Tables (5-8) showed that the highest populations of *T. absoluta* eggs and larvae in Qalyubiya Governorate of tomato, *S. lycopersicom*, potato, *S. tuberosum*, eggplant, *S. melongena* (L.) and pepper, *C. annuum* infested by this pest were 487 and 544; 412 and 482; 381 and 406 and 285 and 384 individuals/ sample, respectively. The highest population of parasitoids and predators on tomatoes in Qalyubiya, the parasitoids *T. evanesens*, *Eulophus* sp., *Diglyphus* sp. The predators *M. caliginosus*, *N. tenuis* was 56, 23, 67, 9 and 25 individuals/sample, respectively. The highest population of parasitoids and predators on potatoes in Qalyubiya, the parasitoids *T. evanesens*, *T. euproctidis*, *Telenomus* sp., *B. nigricans*. The predators *N. tenuis*, *M. pygmaeus* were 56, 29, 11, 25, 75 and 14 individuals/ sample, respectively. The highest population of parasitoids and predators on eggplants in Qalyubiya, the parasitoids *T. achaeae*, *Bracon* sp., *Pteromalus* sp., *B. nigricans*, *N. tutae*. The predators *N. tenuis* was 56, 10, 14, 10, 21 and 82 individuals/ sample, respectively. The highest population of parasitoids and predators on peppers in Qalyubiya, the parasitoids *T. achaeae*, *Telenomus* sp., *B. nigricans*, *N. tutae*. The predators *M. caliginosus*, *N. tenuis*, *C. carnea* were 60, 11, 21, 15, 24, 46 and 10 individuals/ sample, respectively

Table (1): Population dynamics *Tuta absoluta* and its natural enemies in Giza Governorate: Tomato, *solanum lycopersicom* (L.).

Dates	No. <i>Tuta absoluta</i> stages		Parasitoids					Predators			
	Eggs	Larvae	T. a.	T. e.	T.eu	P. sp.	E. sp.	D. sp.	M. c.	N. t.	A. s.
Feb. 20 th	161	357	18	1	0	0	0	0	0	12	0
27 th	350	510	22	3	0	0	0	0	0	15	0
March 1 st	422	632	35	5	0	0	0	0	0	23	0
7 th	543	747	40	8	0	0	0	0	0	28	0
14 th	601	757	53	9	0	0	0	0	0	19	0
21 st	554	795	44	4	0	0	0	0	0	14	0
April 1 st	423	632	30	3	0	0	0	0	0	11	0
7 th	352	510	17	2	0	0	0	0	0	9	0
14 th	329	477	14	1	0	0	0	0	0	17	0
21 st	415	585	35	7	4	0	4	0	1	24	1
May 1 st	488	645	47	11	6	2	1	3	1	35	1
7 th	550	737	55	15	8	3	5	1	4	37	4
14 th	611	792	71	18	12	1	2	0	2	41	2
21 st	615	820	83	21	25	1	0	0	2	41	2
June 1 st	648	899	91	23	30	0	0	0	0	45	1
7 th	653	901	96	27	35	2	0	3	0	51	1

Trichogramma achaeae = T. a. *Trichogramma euproctidis* = T.eu *Pteromalus* sp. = P. sp. *Macrolophus caliginosus* = M. c. *Amblyseius swirskii* = A. s.
Trichogramma evanescens = T. e. *Eulophus* sp. = E. sp. *Diglyphus* sp. = D. sp. *Nesidiocoris tenuis* = N. t.

Table (2): Population dynamics *Tuta absoluta* and its natural enemies in Giza Governorate: Potato *Solanum tuberosum* (Linnaeus).

Dates	No. <i>Tuta absoluta</i> stages		Parasitoids				Predators		
	Eggs	Larvae	T. a.	P. sp.	D. sp.	B. n.	M. c.	N. t.	C. c.
Feb. 20 th	112	305	12	0	0	0	0	9	0
27 th	311	450	18	0	0	0	0	10	0
March 1 st	395	590	21	0	0	0	0	17	0
7 th	498	702	35	0	0	0	0	21	0
14 th	556	750	41	0	0	0	0	16	0
21 st	510	733	42	0	0	0	0	12	0
April 1 st	396	594	15	0	0	0	0	8	0
7 th	301	456	19	0	0	0	0	6	0
14 th	298	420	12	0	0	0	0	12	1
21 st	396	531	22	0	0	0	0	13	0
May 1 st	440	603	34	0	1	0	2	19	0
7 th	488	697	38	1	3	3	3	20	2
14 th	559	765	47	2	0	1	1	23	1
21 st	577	789	43	0	1	0	0	24	1
June 1 st	601	861	54	0	1	0	0	27	0
7 th	655	874	55	1	0	0	0	29	0

Trichogramma achaeae = T. a. *Diglyphus* sp. = D. sp. *Pteromalus* sp. = P. sp. *Macrolophus caliginosus* = M. c. *Chrysoperla carnea* = C. c.
Bracon nigricans = B.n. *Nesidiocoris tenuis* = N. t.

Table (3): Population dynamics *Tuta absoluta* and its natural enemies in Giza Governorate: Eggplant *Solanum melongena* (Linnaeus).

Dates	No. <i>Tuta absoluta</i> stages		Parasitoids				Predators	
	Eggs	Larvae	T. b.	B. sp.	P. sp.	D. sp.	N. t.	A. s.
Feb. 20 th	87	210	0	0	0	0	4	0
27 th	150	320	0	0	0	0	7	0
March 1 st	220	419	0	0	0	0	10	0
7 th	331	540	0	0	0	0	14	0
14 th	430	534	0	0	0	0	9	0
21 st	315	581	6	0	0	0	10	0
April 1 st	219	231	4	0	0	0	5	0
7 th	114	110	8	0	0	0	8	0
14 th	117	245	9	0	0	0	11	4
21 st	201	363	12	2	0	1	13	6
May 1 st	233	433	14	0	1	0	14	3
7 th	345	547	13	1	3	2	21	2
14 th	408	589	8	0	0	0	23	1
21 st	411	615	7	0	0	0	24	1
June 1 st	423	687	5	1	0	2	31	0
7 th	436	688	3	1	0	1	36	0

Trichogrammatoidea bactrae = T. b. *Pteromalus* sp. = P. sp. *Bracon* sp. = B. sp. *Nesidiocoris tenuis* = N. t. *Amblyseius swirskii* = A. s. *Diglyphus* sp. = D. sp

Table (4): Population dynamics *Tuta absoluta* and its natural enemies in Giza Governorate: Pepper, *Capsicum annuum*

Dates	No. <i>Tuta absoluta</i> stages		Parasitoids					Predators			
	Eggs	Larvae	T. a.	T. b.	El. sp.	T. sp.	B. n.	N. tu.	N. t.	M. p.	C. c.
Feb. 20 th	51	142	7	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0
27 th	81	200	13	0	0	0	0	3	3	0	0
March 1 st	101	311	18	0	0	0	0	2	6	0	0
7 th	209	432	22	0	0	0	0	5	7	0	0
14 th	300	414	25	0	0	0	0	4	8	0	0
21 st	532	447	31	0	0	0	3	0	8	0	0
April 1 st	103	319	34	0	0	0	10	0	9	1	0
7 th	50	203	13	1	0	0	12	0	4	3	0
14 th	312	145	15	3	0	0	9	0	9	1	0
21 st	108	233	18	4	0	0	5	0	10	0	0
May 1 st	145	332	21	5	3	0	4	0	11	0	0
7 th	232	409	24	6	2	0	1	0	13	0	0
14 th	301	422	27	2	1	0	0	0	16	0	0
21 st	311	501	30	1	0	0	0	0	18	0	2
June 1 st	336	561	34	0	0	1	0	0	22	0	5
7 th	335	587	37	0	0	0	0	1	25	0	3

Trichogramma achaeae = T. a. *Elasmus* sp. = El. sp. *Bracon nigricans* = B.n. *Nesidiocoris tenuis* = N. t. *Chrysoperla carnea* = C. c.
Necremnus tutae = N. tu. *Telenomus* sp. = T.sp. *Trichogrammatoidea bactrae* = T. b. *Macrolophus pygmaeus* = M. p.

Table (5): Population dynamics *Tuta absoluta* and its natural enemies in Qalyubiya Governorate: Tomato, *solanum lycopersicom* (L.).

Dates	No. <i>Tuta absoluta</i> stages		Parasitoids			Predators	
	Eggs	Larvae	T. e.	E. sp.	D. sp.	M. c.	N. t.
Feb. 20 th	45	123	2	0	0	0	2
27 th	73	195	5	0	3	0	3
March 1 st	92	288	7	0	5	0	6
7 th	188	401	10	0	7	0	7
14 th	290	378	13	0	7	6	8
21 st	487	410	8	4	11	7	8
April 1 st	97	267	6	7	9	9	9
7 th	30	198	8	9	13	6	4
14 th	265	133	12	4	17	5	9
21 st	95	201	14	2	19	0	10
May 1 st	122	324	17	5	34	0	11
7 th	185	396	23	7	45	0	13
14 th	255	402	34	12	51	0	16
21 st	295	477	45	14	56	0	18
June 1 st	301	490	52	17	63	0	22
7 th	321	544	56	23	67	0	25

Trichogramma evanesens = T. e. *Eulophus* sp. = E. sp. *Diglyphus* sp. = D. sp. *Macrolophus caliginosus* = M. c. *Nesidiocoris tenuis* = N. t.

Table (6): Population dynamics *Tuta absoluta* and its natural enemies in Qalyubiya Governorate: Potato *Solanum tuberosum* (Linnaeus).

Dates	No. <i>Tuta absoluta</i> stages		Parasitoids				Predators	
	Eggs	Larvae	T. e.	T.eu	T. sp.	B. n.	N. t.	M. p.
Feb. 20 th	38	78	2	0	1	0	1	0
27 th	56	120	5	0	3	0	2	0
March 1 st	86	211	7	0	0	0	5	0
7 th	136	387	10	0	0	0	6	0
14 th	213	289	13	0	0	2	7	0
21 st	412	395	8	0	0	5	10	2
April 1 st	76	206	6	0	0	14	12	5
7 th	24	96	8	0	0	16	17	7
14 th	210	89	12	0	0	21	16	9
21 st	68	198	14	2	0	9	27	12
May 1 st	99	277	17	4	0	6	36	14
7 th	185	315	23	7	4	8	44	0
14 th	157	366	34	9	2	13	56	0
21 st	164	421	45	21	5	17	68	0
June 1 st	178	431	52	27	6	23	73	0
7 th	285	482	56	29	11	25	75	0

Trichogramma evanesens = T. e. *Telenomus* sp. = T.sp. *Trichogramma euproctidis* = T.eu *Nesidiocoris tenuis* = N. t. *Bracon nigricans* = B.n. *Macrolophus pygmaeus* = M. p.

Table (7): Population dynamics *Tuta absoluta* and its natural enemies in Qalyubiya Governorate: Eggplant *Solanum melongena* (Linnaeus).

Dates	No. <i>Tuta absoluta</i> stages		Parasitoids				Predator	
	Eggs	Larvae	T. a.	B. sp.	P. sp.	B. n.	N. tu.	N. t.
Feb. 20 th	27	71	3	0	0	2	0	4
27 th	49	110	9	0	0	6	0	6
March 1 st	71	198	12	0	0	9	0	9
7 th	96	258	14	0	0	11	0	12
14 th	184	261	15	0	5	0	1	14
21 st	381	310	26	0	4	0	3	18
April 1 st	52	199	31	0	0	0	11	23
7 th	35	86	17	0	4	0	12	25
14 th	179	76	21	1	5	0	18	28
21 st	60	145	23	4	5	0	13	33
May 1 st	83	200	24	2	8	0	9	42
7 th	113	296	28	3	6	3	9	47
14 th	132	304	31	5	12	6	10	57
21 st	140	376	37	6	14	7	13	71
June 1 st	155	382	41	8	9	9	19	78
7 th	215	406	56	10	13	10	21	82

Trichogramma achaeae = T. a. *Bracon* sp. = B. sp. *Bracon nigricans* = B.n. *Nesidiocoris tenuis* = N. t. *Necremnus tutae* = N. tu. *Pteromalus* sp. = P. sp.

Table (8): Population dynamics *Tuta absoluta* and its natural enemies in Qalyubiya Governorate: Pepper, *Capsicum annuum*

Dates	No. <i>Tuta absoluta</i> stages		Parasitoids				Predators		
	Eggs	Larvae	T. a.	T. sp.	B. n.	N. tu.	M. c.	N. t.	C. c.
Feb. 20 th	19	66	1	3	1	1	0	1	0
27 th	38	95	5	4	3	2	0	3	0
March 1 st	56	130	10	0	7	6	0	5	0
7 th	74	234	11	0	8	7	3	7	1
14 th	102	255	13	0	10	8	4	10	1
21 st	285	277	18	0	13	12	8	11	1
April 1 st	40	154	20	1	8	9	13	13	3
7 th	31	75	21	3	5	2	15	14	5
14 th	46	59	26	5	4	0	21	17	7
21 st	55	112	29	7	7	0	24	21	8
May 1 st	67	166	34	9	9	4	3	32	9
7 th	97	211	36	11	10	7	2	33	10
14 th	110	275	46	0	13	9	1	35	0
21 st	113	305	48	0	18	11	1	38	0
June 1 st	124	310	51	0	20	13	3	42	0
7 th	187	384	60	0	21	15	5	46	0

Trichogramma achaeae = T. a. *Telenomus* sp. = T. sp. *Bracon nigricans* = B. n. *Macrolophus caliginosus* = M. c. *Nesidiocoris tenuis* = N. t. *Chrysoperla carnea* = C. c. *Necremnus tutae* = N. tu.

The results of the present work indicated that this pest infested five host plants. These are tomato, *S. lycopersicom*, potato, *S. tuberosum*, eggplant, *S. melongena*, black nightshade, *S. nigrum* (L.) and pepper, *C. annuum*. It is distributed in 14 Governorates in Egypt. These are Alexandria, Aswan, Behara, Beni-Suef, Dommiette, El-Dakahleia, El-Gharbia, El-Isamlia, El-Monifia, El-Qalubia, El-Sharkia, Giza, Kafr El-Sheikh and Marsa Matrouh. The present work also studied the population dynamics of the tomato leaf miners *T. absoluta* on tomato, *S. lycopersicom*, potato, *S. tuberosum*, eggplant, *S. melongena* (L.) and pepper, *C. annuum* in Giza and Qalyubiya Governorates. The general conclusion of the results of population dynamics of the pest and its natural enemies. It peaked in June 2025. Moussa *et al.* (2013) conducted a survey of the tomato leafminer, *T. absoluta*, infestation on tomato plants was carried out in twelve Governorates across Egypt during flowering stage of summer plantation of 2010 and 2011 seasons. The pest causes severe damage to the foliage and fruit. The survey shows that the degree of infestation was 21%, 48% and 28% in Behara, Dommiette and Aswan governorates, respectively. The corresponding values in 2011 were 50% in Banisweef governorate to 100% in El-Gharbia, El-Monifia, El-Dakahleia, Domitt, El-Qalubia, El-Sharkia and El-Isamlia governorates. Also, the number of larvae per 10 plants in 2010 season ranged from 5 to 125 larvae in Banisweef and El-Monifia governorates. Whereas in 2011 season, the corresponding values in Banisweef and El-Monifia governorates ranged from 3 to 380 larvae. The pest was also found to infest newly cultivated area like Tushka at Aswan governorate during the harvesting period of winter planting in 2010 season. El-Said *et al.*

(2022) documented the prevalence and population dynamics of TLM on tomatoes and other host plants along the Nile Delta region in Egypt. For the first time, we recorded Black nightshade as an alternative host plant. In tomato fields, males and immature stages fluctuated with crop phenological cycle, time, seasons and had 2–3 peaks/season

Natural enemies such as parasitoids and predators were used successfully in biological control of *T. absoluta*. Mahdi *et al.* (2011) recorded a parasitoid wasp, *Diglyphus* sp. (Hymenoptera: Eulophidae) and a predatory bug, *Nesidiocoris tenuis* Reuter (Heteroptera: Miridae) in Algeria. Giorgini *et al.* (2012) and Zappalà *et al.* (2012) found 16 hymenopterous species including *Diglyphus crass-inervis* Erdös belong to 13 genera and 6 families in Italy. Gabarra *et al.* (2013) found 13 larval-pupal parasitoid species including *Elasmus phthorimae-ae* Ferriere (Elasmidae) and *D. crassinervis* occasionally parasitize *T. absoluta* in Spain. Payer *et al.* (2015) observed that females of *Diglyphus isaea* Walker are able to predate *T. absoluta* larvae, but they apparently do not parasitize this species in Spain. Al-Gerrawy *et al.* (2013) identified two egg parasitoids, *Tricogramma* sp. (Tricogrammatidae) and *Telenomus* sp. (Scelionidae) from *T. absoluta* in Iraq. Perdakis *et al.* (2016) used different sticky traps to attract the braconid, *Dacnusa sibirica* Telenga and *D. isaea* parasitizing *T. absoluta* in Greece. They also studied their efficiency in capturing the effective predator *N. tenuis*, whose high population levels may cause damages on the to-mato crop.

Molla *et al.* (2009) mentioned that *N. tenuis* was highly effective in controlling *T. absoluta* on tomato under field conditions causing infestation reductions of 97% in leaflets and 100% in fruits in Spain. This predator preyed

actively on eggs and all larval instars of *T. absoluta*, although it preferred first instar larvae under laboratory conditions. Guenaoui and Bensaad (2011) observed young nymphs of *N. tenuis* preying on *T. absoluta* larvae in galleries inside the tomato fruit in France. Molla *et al.* (2011) found that *N. tenuis* can regulate *T. absoluta* populations, because it is able to prey efficiently on pest eggs in Spain. Also, during the present work this pest is recorded associated with 11 parasitoids and 6 predators. The parasitoids were *T. achaeae*, *T. evanesens*, *T. euproctidis*, *T. bactrae*, Bracon sp., *Pteromalus* sp., *Eulophus* sp., *Diglyphus* sp. and *N. tutae* new record in Egypt, *Elasmus* sp., *Telenomus* sp., *B. nigricans* and the predators were *M. caliginosus*, *N. tenuis*, *M. pygmaeus*, *C. carnea* and *A. swirskii* and the most important parasitoids and predators are *T. achaeae* and *N. tenuis*, respectively.

El-Said *et al.* (2022) three predators; *N. tenuis*, *M. pygmaeus* and *C. carnea* an egg parasitoid, *T. achaeae* were recorded. Natural enemies corresponded to pest population fluctuations with higher incidence during the middle of the season. Activities of *T. achaeae* and *N. tenuis* were correlated with egg population in summer while *M. pygmaeus* correlated with larval population in winter. Exploring these ecological aspects provides key elements for pest control programs. El-Arnaouty and Kortam (2012) recorded *N. tenuis* for the first time in Egypt associated with *T. absoluta* in aubergine and tomato plantations in Giza, Qaluobia and Fayoum Governorates.

Various hymenopteran parasitoids belonging to families

Trichogrammatidae, Braconidae, Chalcididae, Eilophidae, Elasmidae, Pteromalidae, and Scelionidae have been recorded to attack TLM (Abbes *et al.*, 2014). Also, predator species from order Hemiptera such as *Campyloneuropsis infumatus* Carvalho, *Dicyphus* sp., *Engytatus varians* Distant, *Macrolophus* sp., *Nesidiocoris* sp., and *Orius* sp. have been reported to prey on TLM (Abdelmaksoud *et al.*, 2016). Also, Abdelmaksoud *et al.* (2016) recorded three genera of hymenopterous parasitoids, *Diglyphus* sp. (Eulophidae), *Elasmus* spp. (Elasmidae) and *Telenomus* sp. (Scelionidae) are the first record in Egypt. The predator bug, *N. tenuis* was also recorded. *T. absoluta* showed two peaks of 30.3 and 25.0 leaf mines/10 leaflets on 7th and 28th of May 2013, respectively. *N. tenuis* also recorded two peaks of 58.8 and 73.3 nymphs and adults/plant on the same previous dates, respectively. *N. tenuis* was mass reared to evaluate the predatory efficiency of nymph and adult stages on *T. absoluta* eggs. The nymph, adult male and female consumed 113.3, 81.5 and 125.3 eggs of *T. absoluta*, respectively. The 4th nymphal instar devoured the highest number (30.6 eggs), while the 1st nymphal instar ate the lowest (7 eggs). Therefore, *N. tenuis* was highly effective in controlling *T. absoluta* eggs under laboratory conditions. Likewise, the three species of mirid predators that were recorded in our study were found on the eggs and young larvae of the TLM in protected tomato crops in Southern France (Zappalà *et al.*, 2012), Egypt (El-Arnaouty and Kortam, 2012 and Abdelmaksoud *et al.* 2016).

References

- Abbes, K.; Biondi, A.; Zappalà, L. and Chermiti, B. (2014)** : Fortuitous parasitoids of the invasive tomato leafminer *Tuta absoluta* in Tunisia. *Phytoparasitica*, 42:85–92. [https:// doi. org/ 10. 1007/s12600-013- 0341-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s12600-013-0341-x)
- Abbes, K.; Harbi, A.; Elimem, M.; et al. (2016)**: Bioassay of three solanaceous weeds as alternative hosts for the invasive tomato leafminer *Tuta absoluta* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) and insights on their carryover potential. *African Entomol.*, 24:334–342. [https:// doi. org/ 10. 4001/ 003. 024. 0334](https://doi.org/10.4001/003.024.0334)
- Abdelmaksoud, E.; El-Refai, A. and Rashwan, R. (2016)**: Survey of parasitoids and predators of tomato leaf miner, *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) in Egypt. *Arab Univ. J. Agric. Sci.*, 24:547–553. [https:// doi. org / 10. 21608/ ajs. 2016. 14353](https://doi.org/10.21608/ajs.2016.14353)
- Abolmaaty, S.M.; Hassanein, M.K. and Khalil, A.A. (2010)**: Impact of climatic changes in Egypt on degree day 's units and generation number for tomato leaf miner moth *Tuta absoluta*, (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). *Nat. Sci.*, 8:122–129.
- Al-Gerrawy, A.J.; Al-Zubaidy, H.K. and Ha-ma, N.N. (2013)**: First record of important natural enemies on tomato borer *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) in greenhouses in middle of Iraq. Second Scientific Conference, Fac. Agric., Carbelaa Univ., pp. 953-960.
- Awad, H.A.; El-Naggar, A.Z. and EL-Bassouiny, H.M. (2018)**: Monitoring population of tomato leaf miner, *Tuta absoluta* during winter and summer evergreens of potato filed in Egypt. *Egypt. Acad. J. Biol. Sci.*, 11:27–32. [https:// doi. org/ 10. 17990/ RPF/ 10. 17990/ RPF/](https://doi.org/10.17990/RPF/10.17990/RPF/)
- Bahamondes L. and Mallea, A. (1969)**: Biología en Mendoza de *Scrobipalpula absoluta* (Meyrick) Povolny (Lepidoptera-Gelechiidae), especie nueva para la República Argentina. *Rev Facultad de Ciencias Agrarias, Universidad Nacional de Cuyo*, 15(1):96–104.
- Branco, C. M.; Francëa, F.H.; Cordeiro, C.M.T. ; Maluf, W.R. and Resende, A.M. (1987)**: Selecaoem F2 (*Lycopersicon esculentum* L. pennellii) visando resisten- ciaa traca-do-tomateiro. *Hort. Brasil*, 5: 30-32.
- Cely, L., Cantor, F.;Rodríguez, D. and Cure, J. (2006)**: Niveles de danos ocasionados por diferentes densidades de *Tuta absoluta* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) en tomate bajo invernadero. *Socolen Encuentroconla Entomologíaenl EjeCafetero. XXXIII Congreso de Entomología, Manizales, Colombia*, 26–28 .
- El-Arnaouty, S.A. and Kortam M.N. (2012)**: First record of the mirid predatory species, *Nesidio-coris tenuis* Reuter (Heteroptera: Miridae) on the tomato leafminer, *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) in Egypt. *Egypt. J. Biol. Pest Cont.*, 22(2), 223-224.
- El-Said, M.; Hassan; F.; Ibrahim, I. M.; Ali, F. A. and El-Shesheny, I. A. (2022)**: Prevalence, population dynamics and associated natural enemies of Tomato Leafminer, *Tuta absoluta*, in Egypt. *International Journal of Tropical Insect Science*, 42:143–162. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42690-021-00526-3>
- Gabarra, R.; Arno, J.; Lara, L.; Verdu, M.J.; Ribes, A.; Beitia, F.; Urbaneja, A.; Teñlez, M.M.; Molla', O. and Riudavets, J. (2013)**:

- Native parasitoids associated with *Tuta absoluta* in the tomato production areas of the Spanish Mediterranean Coast. *Bio Control*, 59: 45–54.
- Giorgini, M.; Bernardo, U. and Pedata, P.A. (2012):** The parasitoid complex of *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick) in Italy. *Italia. Entomol. Anno*, 60: 77-84.
- Guenaoui, Y. and Bensaad, R. (2011):** Behaviour of *Tuta absoluta* larvae attacking tomato fruit. Les Cochenilles: ravageur principal ou secondaire. 9eme Conference Internationale sur les Ravageurs en Agriculture, Sup Agro, Montpellier, France, 25-27 Octobre, pp. 318-323.
- Mahdi, K.; Doumandji-Mitiche, B.; Ababsia, A. and Doumandji S. (2011):** Natural enemies of the tomato leaf miner *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick, 1917) in Algeria: prospects for biological control. 4eme Conference Internationale sur les Methodes Alternatives en Protection des Cultures. Evolution des cadres réglementaires européens et français. Nouveaux moyens et stratégies innovantes, Nouveau Siècle, Lille, France, pp. 561-567.
- Mohammed, A.S. (2010):** New record for leaf miner, *Tuta absoluta* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) infested tomato plantations in Kafr El-Sheikh region. *J. Agric. Res. Kafer El-Sheikh Univ.*, 36:238–239.
- Molla, O.; Gonzalez-Cabrera, J. and Urbaneja, A. (2011):** The combined use of *Bacillus thuringiensis* and *Nesidiocoris tenuis* against the tomato borer *Tuta absoluta*. *BioControl*, 56(6): 883-891.
- Molla, O.; Monton, H.; Vanaclocha, P.; Beitia, F. and Urbaneja, A. (2009):** Predation by the mirids *Nesidiocoris tenuis* and *Macrolophus pygmaeus* on the tomato borer *Tuta absoluta*. *IOBC/WPRS Bull.*, 49: 209-214.
- Moussa, S.; Sharma, A.; Baiomy, F. and El-Adl, F. E. (2013):** The Status of Tomato Leaf miner; *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) in Egypt and Potential Effective Pesticides. *Academic Journal of Entomology*, 6 (3): 110-115.doi: 10.5829/idosi.aje.2013.6.3.75130
- Nakano, O. and Paulo, A.D. (1983):** As tracas do tomateiro. *groquômica*, 20: 8-12.
- Payer, R.; Figueiredo, E. and Mexia, A. (2015):** Evaluation of parasitism and predation of *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick, 1917) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) by *Diglyphus isaea*. *Shilap Revta. Lepid.*, 43 (170): 173-179.
- Perdikis, D. Ch.; Arvaniti, K.A. and Papadimitriou, D.M. (2016):** Effects of sticky traps on *Dacnusa sibirica*, *Diglyphus isaea* and *Nesidiocoris tenuis*. *Entomol. Hellen.*, 25 : 1-6.
- Zappalà, L.; Bernardo, U.; Biondi, A.; Cocco, A.; Deliperi, S.; Delrio, G.; Giorgini, M.; Pedata, P.; Rapisarda, C.; Garzia, G.T. and Siscaro, G. (2012):** Recruitment of native parasitoids by the exotic pest *Tuta absoluta* in Southern Italy. *Bull. Insectol.*, 65 (1): 51-61.